

OBITUARY

Dr. PRAFULLA CHANDRA MITTER

Born: 1882.

Died: July 12, 1957.

The death of Dr. Prafulla Chandra Mitter on 12th July, 1957 at the age of 76 years, has removed from amongst us one of the most successful teachers in chemistry. In him we found an effective combination of those virtues that are essential for success as a teacher as well as a researcher. His researches embraced a variety of fields of organic chemistry, namely, anthraquinones, pyrimidines, imminazoles, flavones, isoflavones, naturally occurring coloring matters and long-chain fatty acids, and in each of them he made significant contributions. His investigations on the synthesis of munjistin and aloemodin and his experiments on the transformation and synthesis of aleuritic acid deserve special mention.

But greater still was he as a teacher. His class lectures were lucidity itself. Not only did he promote research and scholarship through his own researches and teaching, but he also inspired, and offered exemplary freedom to, generations of his students and collaborators to think on their own and to initiate independent research of higher order through their own efforts. Thus we find to-day many of the professorial chairs in organic chemistry all over India occupied with distinction by his students who received their initial training and inspiration in his laboratory. Apart from the academic and educational profession, many of his students are to-day in important and key positions in various Government and Industrial research establishments. This is no mean achievement, and if the success of a teacher is measured by the success of his students, Dr. P. C. Mitter probably ranks second to none but the late Acharya P. C. Ray. He was himself a student of the Acharya whom he succeeded in 1937 as Palit Professor and Head of the Department of Chemistry of the Calcutta University. A worthy pupil indeed of a great Master!

Dr. P. C. Mitter had unusual flair for languages and was conversant with all the important languages of Europe. Even after his retirement in 1946 from the chair of Palit Professor and Head of the Calcutta University Chemistry Department, he mastered the Russian language with the help of a linguaphone. The intimate knowledge of more than half a dozen languages and their literature probably accounts for his wisdom, cultured demeanour and witty conversation.

Born in 1882, Prafulla Chandra Mitter graduated from the Presidency College, Calcutta and obtained his Ph. D. degree in 1912; working under the guidance of Professor Carl Liebermann in Berlin University. He joined the Calcutta University Chemistry Department in 1916 as its Ghosh Professor and was primarily responsible for the planning of the majestic building of the University College of Science and Technology in Calcutta.

Dr. P. C. Mitter was actively associated with the most of the scientific Societies and organisations in India. He was Treasurer of the Indian Science Congress Association and the Indian Science News Association and a member of the Indian Research Fund Association. He was a Fellow of the National Institute of Sciences of India.

As a Foundation Member of the Indian Chemical Society, Dr. P. C. Mitter had served the Society since 1924 in various capacities, e. g., Council Member, Honorary Treasurer, Honorary Secretary, Vice-President, Associate Editor and a Member of the Publication Committee.

Indian Science owes much of its development to his pioneering work.

S. M. Mukherji.

GANESH CHANDRA MITTER

Born: August 1, 1897.

Died: February 10, 1957.

Ganesh Chandra Mitter was born in a very respectable and well-known Kayastha family of Howrah District, Bengal. He obtained his B.Sc. degree with First Class Hons. in Chemistry from the St. Xavier's College, Calcutta in 1918 and M.Sc. degree in 1920, having stood first in Chemistry from the University College of Science, Calcutta. He was awarded the Sir Rashbehari Ghosh (Post-graduate) scholarship during 1921-1922.

In 1922 he was appointed Deputy Assay Master (Govt. of India); being the first Indian to hold the post in the Bombay Mint. Later he was promoted to the office of the Chief Assayer of the Indian Mints (1932-1947). During this period the most outstanding events were firstly, the unprecedented export of gold which was successfully tackled in the Assay Office under his control, and secondly, the introduction of Q-alloy coinage, the metallurgical assay of which was vested in the Assay Office, and thirdly, the colossal coinage programme during the war years, record of which in volume stands only second to that of the Philadelphia Mint. During 1947-1952 he held the office of the Chief Technical Adviser (Ministry of Finance, Govt. of India). During this period the important work entrusted to him was investigation and planning of a Silver Refinery capable of recovering silver from the Quarternary alloy coins so that the 225 million ounces of Lend/Lease silver might be returned to the U.S.A. Since 1952 till his death he held the office of the Master, Assay Department and was entrusted with the work of setting up of the Silver Refinery at the Old Calcutta Mint, 47 Strand Road, Calcutta, which would work a new process of which he had been a joint inventor.

He devoted considerable time in the researches on the alloys used in minting currency coins and obtained several patents.

He was a member of the Advisory Board of the Royal Institute of Sciences and Victoria Jubilee Technical Institute, Bombay and a member of several scientific and technical committees of C.S.I.R. and of different Ministries and Departments of the